

INTRODUCTION

This computational parametric study analyzes the effect of geometrical design parameters of a microring resonator on its optical characteristics with the goal to optimize its performance for label-free detection of biomarkers.

Fig. 1: Schematic of a planar waveguide-coupled microring resonator channel add-drop filter.

1- Effect of width of waveguides and microring (w)

Table 1: Effect of the width of waveguide and microring on the quality factor of resonance output at pickup waveguide ($R=50\ \mu\text{m}$; $g=0.2\ \mu\text{m}$; wavelength range= 1309 to 1311 nm).

Width of waveguides and microring (μm)	Quality Factor
0.350	$\sim 5 \times 10^4$
0.300	$\sim 2.6 \times 10^4$
0.250	$\sim 9.5 \times 10^3$

Fig. 2 Normalized transverse electric field intensity across the microring width at resonant wavelengths between 1309-1311 nm ($R=50\ \mu\text{m}$; $g=0.2\ \mu\text{m}$).

METHODS

2- Effect of microring outer radius (R)

To observe consistent resonance shift due to particle absorption on the ring, at least two resonance peaks should be available and obtained within a 2 nm narrow operating range of wavelength at a microring outer radius of 50 μm . The quality factor of all cases remained approximately of the same order (10^4).

Table 2: Effect of the microring outer radius on FSR ($w=0.35\ \mu\text{m}$; $g=0.2\ \mu\text{m}$; wavelength range= 1309 to 1311 nm).

Outer radius (μm)	Free Spectral Range (FSR) (nm)
10	7.9476
20	3.9487
30	2.6114
40	1.9598
50	1.5042

3- Effect of coupling gap (g)

Fig.3. Normalized Intensity at the drop port for varying coupling gap ($< 0.2\ \mu\text{m}$) (left inset), and ($> 0.2\ \mu\text{m}$) (right inset) between the microring and waveguides ($R=50\ \mu\text{m}$; $w=0.35\ \mu\text{m}$).

For coupling gap $< 0.2\ \mu\text{m}$, the quality factor reduces with decreasing coupling gap between the microring and the waveguides and the energy coupled from the feed waveguide into the microring easily coupled back to the feed waveguide as the wave circulated within the ring. Similar phenomena occurred between the microring and pickup waveguide which affected the quality factor of the resonant conditions.

For the coupling gap $> 0.2\ \mu\text{m}$ the quality factor did not vary significantly but the strength of output signal reduced which is not useful for experimental purposes. This may be due to a leakage of electromagnetic energy in the wider coupling gap.

RESULTS

4- Detection of Nanoparticle

Fig. 3 Schematic of a microring resonator with a 150 nm nanoparticle attached on the outer ring: (a) the overall dimensions of the microring resonator system, (b) enlarged view at contact point between resonator and particle, (c) hybrid mesh view at contact point between resonator and particle.

Fig.4 Resonance shift due to the absorption of a nanoparticle on the optimized microring resonator ($R=50\ \mu\text{m}$; $g=0.2\ \mu\text{m}$; $w=0.35\ \mu\text{m}$)

The experimental equipment has the capability of detecting a resonance shift of 1.2 pm therefore a single exosome can theoretically be detected and its size be measured.

CONCLUSIONS

- Using electromagnetic frequency domain finite element analysis, optimum values of parameters to design a microring resonator ($w=0.35\ \mu\text{m}$; $R=50\ \mu\text{m}$; $g=0.2\ \mu\text{m}$) were obtained for the wavelength of 1309 - 1311 nm laser.
- Ability to detect 100-150 nm particles was also demonstrated numerically.